

TRIFON I. MISSOV* – LÁSZLÓ NÉMETH** ♣

Sensitivity of model-based human mortality measures to exclusion of the Makeham or the frailty parameter

1. INTRODUCTION

Governments, insurance companies, pension funds, health policy makers and population researchers calculate human mortality measures from life tables. Life-table data are usually right censored as age-specific death counts at the highest ages are aggregated in an open-end age interval. Addressing censoring adequately is crucial to characterize correctly the distribution of deaths: Missov *et al.* (2016) illustrate that conventional life-table treatment of censoring (see e.g. Preston *et al.*, 2001), i.e. assuming a constant hazard in the last open-age interval, leads to distortions in mortality indicators like life expectancy, the modal age at death, life disparity, entropy, and the Gini coefficient, especially when the age at censoring is lower than 85. Mortality indicators are much more robust in the case of fitting a parametric model that accounts for right censoring in a standard survival-analysis setting (Missov *et al.*, 2016).

What model and in what age range should be fitted to reconstruct mortality in the last open-end interval? Numerous studies (e.g. Gompertz, 1825; Makeham, 1860; Beard, 1959; Vaupel *et al.*, 1979; Vaupel *et al.*, 1985) point at the log-linear increase of death rates at ages 30-85 (approximately) which implies a Gompertz hazard. Deviations from the log-linear pattern at ages below 30 and above 85 lead to three extensions of the Gompertz model: the Gompertz-Makeham, the gamma-Gompertz, and the gamma-Gompertz-Makeham models that we will address (incl. the Gompertz model) as the *Gompertz family*. All distributions in the *Gompertz family* are characterized by an exponential increase, ae^{bx} , in the individual age-specific force of mortality (the Gompertz component), where x denotes age, a is the death rate at the initial age, and b is the slope of log-mortality increase. Distributions of the *Gompertz family* may also contain an age-independent additive hazard, c , accounting for extrinsic mortality (the Makeham component), and/or a dispersion parameter, γ accounting for the distribution of unobserved heterogeneity (the frailty or gamma component). An overview of the four models is given in Section 2 and Figure 1 shows the associated hazards in a comparative perspective.

* Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Rostock, Germany and Institute of Sociology and Demography, University of Rostock, Rostock, Germany.

** Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Rostock, Germany.
Corresponding author: Trifon I. Missov, e-mail: missov@demogr.mpg.de.

♣ The authors contributed equally to the manuscript.

The model that best describes adult human mortality patterns is the gamma-Gompertz-Makeham because, statistically, its S-shaped hazard captures observed deviations from the log-linear pattern at both ends, and, semantically, it accounts for unobserved heterogeneity in the study population. However, fitting a gamma-Gompertz-Makeham model to adult human mortality data is not always the “golden standard” as some researchers prefer fitting other models of the Gompertz family: leaving out c when the starting age of analysis lies in the log-linear mortality segment (e.g. Salinari and de Santis, 2014) or omitting γ if mortality deceleration at the oldest ages is not to be detected (e.g. Gavrilov and Gavrilova, 2011; Gavrilova and Gavrilov, 2015) perhaps due to age-specific mortality improvement over calendar time and the resulting shift of the onset of mortality deceleration to older and older ages. In this article we study how human mortality measures are affected if non-zero c or γ is neglected in the chosen model of the *Gompertz family*.

2. THE GOMPERTZ FAMILY

Parametric adult-mortality models capture different patterns of death-rate increase over age: power, exponential, logistic, etc. Since Beard (1959) actuaries, demographers, reliability engineers, evolutionary biologists and epidemiologists have acknowledged the fact that a given mortality pattern can be generated by a homogeneous population of individuals exposed to one and the same hazard or, equivalently, by a heterogeneous population of individuals subjected to a finite or countably infinite number of different hazards. Gompertz (1825) suggested an exponential increase of one’s risk of dying from senescent causes

$$\mu_G(x) = ae^{bx}, \quad [1]$$

where a denotes the level of mortality at the starting adult age of analysis and b , equal to the relative derivative of $\mu_G(x)$, captures the rate of individual aging. If the exponentially increasing hazard of death from senescent causes is complemented at each age by a constant non-aging-related risk c (Makeham, 1860), the resulting model is characterized by a force of mortality

$$\mu_{GM}(x) = ae^{bx} + c. \quad [2]$$

If the study population is considered heterogeneous with respect to a , i.e. individual mortality patterns have the same rate of aging b , but different starting levels of mortality a , the resulting relative-risk models are known as *frailty models* (Vaupel *et al.*, 1979; Duchateau and Janssen, 2008; Wienke, 2010). Formally, an unobserved random variable Z , called frailty (Vaupel *et al.*, 1979), modulates the initial mortality level, and the hazard function for individuals with frailty $Z = z$ is given by

$$\mu_{\Gamma G}(x|z) = zae^{bx}, \quad [3]$$

when the risk of dying for all individuals follows a Gompertz pattern, and

$$\mu_{\Gamma GM}(x|z) = zae^{bx} + c, \quad [4]$$

when, in addition, each individual is subjected to one and the same additive hazard c at all ages x . The Makeham term c is often said to capture background or extrinsic mortality. For empirical (Beard, 1959; Vaupel *et al.*, 1979) and theoretical reasons (Finkelstein and Esaulova, 2006; Steinsaltz and Wachter, 2006; Missov and Finkelstein, 2011) frailty is often assumed to be gamma-distributed with an expected value of 1 and a squared coefficient of variation γ , i.e., $Z \sim \Gamma(1/\gamma, 1/\gamma)$ follows a single-parameter gamma distribution. As frailty is unobserved and human mortality data are aggregated for the entire population by age and year (or age and cohort), researchers fit the marginal models resulting from [3] and [4], namely

$$\mu_{\Gamma G}(x) = \frac{ae^{bx}}{1 + \frac{a\gamma}{b}(e^{bx} - 1)} \quad [5]$$

and

$$\mu_{\Gamma GM}(x) = \frac{ae^{bx}}{1 + \frac{a\gamma}{b}(e^{bx} - 1)} + c. \quad [6]$$

Models [1], [2], [5], and [6] all assume an exponentially increasing individual age-specific hazard of death that captures the senescence process, and that is why it makes sense to address these models as the *Gompertz family* (Figure 1 shows the logarithmic hazards in a comparative perspective). For convenience, we will denote the Gompertz model [1] by G, the Gompertz-Makeham [2] by GM, the gamma-Gompertz [5] by ΓG , and the gamma-Gompertz-Makeham [6] by ΓGM . Vaupel and Missov (2014) present an extensive overview of relationships that hold within each of the four models from the *Gompertz family*, while Missov (2013) and Missov and Lenart (2013) study the corresponding first moments or, demographically speaking, life expectancies.

Section 4 studies how model misspecification can influence the estimates of model parameters and which associated mortality measures may be affected. A model of the *Gompertz family* can be misspecified by neglecting either non-zero extrinsic mortality (omitting c) or statistically significant frailty (omitting γ). Disregarding c is usually driven by the fact that estimating a model with a Makeham term (GM or ΓGM) is qualitatively different from estimating a model without it (G or ΓG): the former is a pure optimization problem (likelihood maximization) while the latter reduces to running a

Poisson regression (Brillinger, 1986; McCullagh and Nelder, 1989). Disregarding γ stems usually either from one's disbelief in the heterogeneity of the study population or from not finding compelling evidence for the existence of mortality deceleration at the oldest ages (Gavrilov and Gavrilova, 2011; Gavrilova and Gavrilov, 2015).

Figure 1 – *Logarithmic hazards of the models from the Gompertz family for standard human-mortality parameter values: $a = 0.00001$, $b = 0.14$, $c = 0.001$, and $\gamma = 0.2$. Note that the Makeham term captures the “tail” to the left of the log-Gompertz line, whereas γ accounts for mortality deceleration at the oldest ages*

3 MODEL FITTING

The fitting procedure for the models of the Gompertz family is based on the assumption that death counts $D(x)$ at age x are Poisson-distributed, i.e. $D(x) \sim \text{Poisson}(E(x)\mu(x))$ (Brillinger, 1986), where $E(x)$ is the exposure at age x and $\mu(x)$ denotes the corresponding hazard from [1], [2], [5] or [6]. As a result, we maximize a Poisson log-likelihood

$$\ln L = \sum_x [D(x) \ln \mu(x) - E(x)\mu(x)]. \quad [7]$$

Note that models [1] and [5], the G and the ΓG , are estimated in a qualitatively different way than models [2] and [6] that contain a Makeham term, the GM and the ΓGM . Taking advantage of the fact that the ΓG marginal survival function is given by

$$s_{\Gamma G}(x) = \left(1 + \frac{a\gamma}{b}(e^{bx} - 1) \right)^{-1/\gamma},$$

one can rewrite [5] as (Vaupel, 2002)

$$\mu_{\Gamma G}(x) = ae^{bx}[s_{\Gamma G}(x)]^\gamma. \tag{8}$$

Expressions [1] and [8] aid representing log-mortality in the G and the ΓG setting as

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \mu_G(x) &= \ln a + bx \\ \ln \mu_{\Gamma G}(x) &= \ln a + bx + \gamma \ln s_{\Gamma G}(x), \end{aligned}$$

i.e., parameters a , b , and γ can be estimated by a generalized linear model, whose solution is calculated analytically by applying iteratively-reweighted least squares (McCullagh and Nelder, 1989). Due to the additive Makeham term, expressions [2] and [6] cannot be expressed in a regression form, and we maximize the log-likelihood $\ln L$ in [7]. This is an optimization problem over a three- (in the case of GM) or four-dimensional (in the case of ΓGM) space. Finding its solution is not always an easy task as standard gradient-based optimization algorithms might converge to a local maximum instead of the global one. For models of the *Gompertz family* gradient-based methods show little robustness when at least one of the parameters (usually a and/or c) is close to zero. As a result, due to the high sensitivity of parameter estimates to the starting values, many researchers avoid fitting a model with a Makeham term, i.e. the starting age of analysis is chosen in the interval of log-linear increase of death rates where the effect of the Makeham term is very small. In this article optimization is carried out by applying differential evolution (Storn and Price, 1997) using the DEoptim R-package (Mullen *et al.*, 2011). Differential evolution (DE) is a fast-converging, robust, and easy-to-use global optimization method for possibly non-linear and non-differentiable continuous-space functions (for a detailed description and examples we redirect readers to Price *et al.*, 2005).

4. MODEL MISSPECIFICATION AND MORTALITY MEASURES

Gompertz-family model misspecification may occur if, for some reason, at least one of the Makeham and gamma components is left out of the model given it is non-zero. Neglecting γ results in estimating a G or a GM hazard when the true one is ΓG or a ΓGM , respectively (Figure 2, top row), while neglecting c results in estimating a G or a ΓG hazard when the true one is GM or a ΓGM , respectively (Figure 2, bottom row). In both cases a is overestimated, while b is underestimated (Table 1). The reverse direction of the bias is not surprising as the maximum-likelihood estimators of \hat{a} and \hat{b} are subjected

to an almost perfect negative correlation (for further discussion, see Lenart and Missov, 2014; Missov *et al.*, 2015). When non-zero γ is left out of the model, c is underestimated, and vice versa (Table 1). Moreover there exists c^* such that for $c > c^*$ neglecting c results in estimating $\gamma = 0$, i.e. the model will not detect frailty at all (see, for example, Table 7). In adult human mortality research, the case when both c and γ are neglected is uncommon, but it affects the estimates of a and b in the same manner as already described.

Figure 2 – Survival and logarithmic-hazard functions of the fitted (red) and the true (blue) model when non-zero γ (top row) or c (bottom row) is neglected

Table 1 – Parameter values corresponding to the graphs in Figure 2

Model				True-Model Parameters			
True	Fitted			a	b	γ	c
ΓG	G			0.00002	0.09	0.4	–
ΓGM	GM			0.00002	0.09	0.4	0.0010
GM	G			0.00002	0.09	–	0.0008
ΓGM	ΓG			0.00002	0.09	0.2	0.0004
Fitting Misspecified Model				Fitting Correct Model			
a	b	γ	c	a	b	γ	c
0.00009	0.07	–	–	0.00002	0.09	0.4	–
0.00013	0.06	–	0.0005	0.00002	0.09	0.4	0.0010
0.00007	0.08	–	–	0.00002	0.09	–	0.0008
0.00006	0.08	0.07	–	0.00002	0.09	0.2	0.0004

4.1. Mortality measures unaffected by misspecification

Figure 2 illustrates that maximum-likelihood estimation keeps the area under the fitted survival curve as close as possible to the area of the true one. Moreover, the true and the fitted survival curves are very close. This suggests intuitively that model misspecification might not affect substantially aggregate mortality measures, such as remaining life expectancy at age x , $e(x)$; life disparity at age x , $e^\dagger(x)$; entropy at age x , $H(x)$; or the Gini coefficient at age x , $G^*(x)$ ¹, that are calculated by integrating the survival function $s(x)$ (or its square) over $[x, \infty)$ ²:

$$e(x) = \frac{1}{s(x)} \int_x^\infty s(t) dt, \quad [9]$$

$$e^\dagger(x) = -\frac{1}{s(x)} \int_x^\infty s(t) \ln s(t) dt, \quad [10]$$

$$H(x) = \frac{-\int_x^\infty s(t) \ln s(t) dt}{\int_x^\infty s(t) dt} = \frac{e^\dagger(x)}{e(x)}, \quad [11]$$

$$G^*(x) = 1 - \frac{\int_x^\infty s^2(t) dt}{\int_x^\infty s(t) dt} = 1 - \frac{\frac{1}{s(x)} \int_x^\infty s^2(t) dt}{e(x)}. \quad [12]$$

To illustrate this, we fit the four models of the Gompertz family to French mortality data (males and females separately) in 1999 from different starting ages x , $x = 25, 30, \dots, 90$, and compare the resulting $e(x)$, $e^\dagger(x)$, $H(x)$, and $G^*(x)$. We use exact (integer) age-specific death counts (raw data) from the Human Mortality Database (HMD, 2015) as HMD provides, in addition, (not necessarily integer) deaths (Wilmoth *et al.*, 2007) that are smoothed according to a

¹ The standard notation for the Gini coefficient is $G(x)$. To avoid confusion with the abbreviation for the Gompertz model, we use $G^*(x)$ to address the Gini coefficient. For conciseness we might also avoid the term “remaining” and sometimes drop the x -argument of the measures.

² Remaining life expectancy $e(x)$ provides the average remaining lifespan of survivors to age x . Life disparity $e^\dagger(x)$ measures how much lifespans of survivors to age x differ among each other and how many of life years are lost due to death (Keyfitz, 1977). Entropy $H(x)$ measures heterogeneity in the age at death of survivors to age x or, alternatively, the elasticity of remaining life expectancy with respect to proportional changes in age-specific mortality (Keyfitz, 1977). The Gini coefficient $G^*(x)$ measures inter-individual inequality in the length of life (Gini, 1912).

Kannisto model (statistically indistinguishable from the ΓG). The four model-based measures (Table 2 for females and Table 3 for males) are almost identical. The Makeham term has slight impact (at the second or third digit after the decimal) on remaining life expectancy and the Gini coefficient when the model is fitted from lower starting ages (25-60), while the inclusion of gamma leads to even smaller differences (at the third digit after the decimal) if the model is fitted from later ages (60-90). Life disparity and entropy are more sensitive to the inclusion of a Makeham term in the model as the latter leads to an additional $-cx$ term for $\ln s(x)$ in the integrand of [10]-[11].

Table 2 – Remaining life expectancy $e(x)$, life disparity $e^\dagger(x)$, entropy $H(x)$, and Gini coefficient $G^*(x)$ at age x for French females in 1999 calculated for each model of the Gompertz family. All models were fitted from different starting ages x onwards (column 1) and the four mortality measures were calculated by [9]-[12] using the survival functions with the corresponding estimated parameters

x	$e(x)$				$e^\dagger(x)$			
	G	GM	ΓG	ΓGM	G	GM	ΓG	ΓGM
30	53.350	53.302	53.350	53.306	8.989	8.984	8.989	8.986
35	48.489	48.459	48.503	48.467	8.866	8.849	8.854	8.852
40	43.694	43.669	43.699	43.682	8.691	8.675	8.679	8.679
45	38.989	38.961	38.989	38.976	8.445	8.442	8.446	8.445
50	34.378	34.333	34.381	34.345	8.133	8.153	8.131	8.163
55	29.848	29.799	29.855	29.795	7.771	7.804	7.767	7.827
60	25.347	25.334	25.361	25.340	7.407	7.417	7.400	7.437
65	20.981	20.981	20.996	20.999	6.971	6.971	6.966	6.984
70	16.799	16.799	16.813	16.823	6.447	6.447	6.448	6.457
75	12.886	12.886	12.906	12.912	5.812	5.812	5.819	5.821
80	9.395	9.395	9.462	9.463	5.046	5.046	5.042	5.041
85	6.560	6.560	6.568	6.567	4.159	4.159	4.172	4.171
90	4.438	4.438	4.441	4.441	3.268	3.268	3.277	3.277

x	$H(x)$				$G^*(x)$			
	G	GM	ΓG	ΓGM	G	GM	ΓG	ΓGM
30	0.168	0.169	0.168	0.169	0.116	0.120	0.116	0.120
35	0.183	0.183	0.183	0.183	0.126	0.129	0.126	0.129
40	0.199	0.199	0.199	0.199	0.137	0.140	0.136	0.140
45	0.217	0.217	0.217	0.217	0.149	0.152	0.149	0.151
50	0.237	0.237	0.236	0.238	0.162	0.165	0.162	0.164
55	0.260	0.262	0.260	0.263	0.177	0.180	0.177	0.179
60	0.292	0.293	0.292	0.293	0.197	0.199	0.196	0.197
65	0.332	0.332	0.332	0.333	0.222	0.222	0.219	0.220
70	0.384	0.384	0.384	0.384	0.252	0.252	0.248	0.248
75	0.451	0.451	0.451	0.451	0.289	0.289	0.284	0.284
80	0.537	0.537	0.533	0.533	0.332	0.332	0.325	0.325
85	0.634	0.634	0.635	0.635	0.376	0.376	0.372	0.372
90	0.736	0.736	0.738	0.738	0.417	0.417	0.415	0.415

Table 3 – Remaining life expectancy $e(x)$, life disparity $e^\dagger(x)$, entropy $H(x)$, and Gini coefficient $G^*(x)$ at age x for French males in 1999 calculated for each model of the Gompertz family. All models were fitted from different starting ages x onwards (column 1) and the four mortality measures were calculated by [9]-[12] using the survival functions with the corresponding estimated parameters

x	$e(x)$				$e^\dagger(x)$			
	G	GM	FG	FGM	G	GM	FG	FGM
30	46.319	46.281	46.779	46.281	10.719	10.695	10.242	10.695
35	41.601	41.574	41.610	41.574	10.497	10.465	10.491	10.465
40	36.962	36.941	37.157	36.941	10.226	10.185	10.017	10.185
45	32.495	32.481	34.844	32.481	9.835	9.794	7.430	9.794
50	28.218	28.190	29.608	28.191	9.323	9.305	7.867	9.305
55	24.119	24.068	24.479	24.065	8.717	8.730	8.326	8.732
60	20.151	20.127	20.152	20.122	8.069	8.075	8.065	8.078
65	16.433	16.430	16.433	16.425	7.323	7.325	7.323	7.330
70	13.053	13.056	13.053	13.059	6.463	6.463	6.463	6.472
75	10.012	10.012	10.009	10.020	5.529	5.529	5.532	5.537
80	7.341	7.341	7.374	7.373	4.572	4.572	4.576	4.575
85	5.146	5.146	5.149	5.149	3.652	3.652	3.659	3.659
90	3.551	3.551	3.552	3.552	2.818	2.818	2.823	2.823

x	$H(x)$				$G^*(x)$			
	G	GM	FG	FGM	G	GM	FG	FGM
30	0.231	0.231	0.219	0.231	0.158	0.160	0.146	0.160
35	0.252	0.252	0.252	0.252	0.172	0.174	0.172	0.174
40	0.277	0.276	0.270	0.276	0.187	0.190	0.181	0.190
45	0.303	0.302	0.213	0.302	0.204	0.206	0.123	0.206
50	0.330	0.330	0.266	0.330	0.220	0.223	0.161	0.223
55	0.361	0.363	0.340	0.363	0.239	0.242	0.219	0.242
60	0.400	0.401	0.400	0.401	0.261	0.264	0.261	0.264
65	0.446	0.446	0.446	0.446	0.286	0.288	0.286	0.288
70	0.495	0.495	0.495	0.496	0.311	0.312	0.311	0.312
75	0.552	0.552	0.553	0.553	0.339	0.339	0.338	0.338
80	0.623	0.623	0.620	0.621	0.371	0.371	0.367	0.367
85	0.710	0.710	0.711	0.711	0.407	0.407	0.405	0.405
90	0.793	0.793	0.795	0.795	0.438	0.438	0.437	0.437

The small effects of c (for lower) and γ (for higher starting ages of fitting) can be even clearly seen in a simulation study: 500000 lifetimes have been generated from a Γ GM distribution with parameters $a = 0.00002$, $b = 0.11$, $c = 0.0004$, $\gamma = 0.02$, and then aggregated age-wise to reflect a typical human mortality data setting. Table 4 presents values of $e(x)$, $e^\dagger(x)$, $H(x)$, and $G^*(x)$ based on estimated parameters from fitting the four models of the Gompertz family.

Table 4 – Remaining life expectancy $e(x)$, life disparity $e^\dagger(x)$, entropy $H(x)$, and Gini coefficient $G^*(x)$ at age x for simulated data (Γ GM with $a = 0.00002$, $b = 0.11$, $c = 0.004$, $\gamma = 0.02$) calculated for each model of the Gompertz family. All models were fitted from different starting ages x onwards (column 1) and the four mortality measures were calculated by [9]-[12] using the survival functions with the corresponding estimated parameters

x	$e(x)$				$e^\dagger(x)$			
	G	GM	Γ G	Γ GM	G	GM	Γ G	Γ GM
30	67.358	67.216	67.358	67.225	9.728	9.867	9.728	9.859
35	62.474	62.361	62.474	62.370	9.633	9.744	9.633	9.735
40	57.586	57.498	57.587	57.507	9.542	9.629	9.541	9.620
45	52.709	52.642	52.709	52.650	9.443	9.510	9.443	9.501
50	47.851	47.803	47.861	47.811	9.331	9.379	9.317	9.370
55	43.022	42.989	43.032	42.997	9.198	9.231	9.185	9.223
60	38.243	38.223	38.244	38.230	9.030	9.050	9.029	9.043
65	33.532	33.521	33.534	33.528	8.815	8.826	8.813	8.820
70	28.930	28.928	28.935	28.932	8.530	8.532	8.525	8.528
75	24.474	24.474	24.480	24.478	8.158	8.158	8.151	8.153
80	20.240	20.240	20.245	20.245	7.666	7.666	7.659	7.660
85	16.297	16.297	16.303	16.301	7.037	7.037	7.031	7.031
90	12.718	12.718	12.722	12.719	6.272	6.272	6.268	6.267

x	$H(x)$				$G^*(x)$			
	G	GM	Γ G	Γ GM	G	GM	Γ G	Γ GM
30	0.144	0.147	0.144	0.147	0.100	0.103	0.100	0.103
35	0.154	0.156	0.154	0.156	0.107	0.110	0.107	0.109
40	0.166	0.167	0.166	0.167	0.115	0.117	0.114	0.117
45	0.179	0.181	0.179	0.180	0.124	0.126	0.124	0.125
50	0.195	0.196	0.195	0.196	0.134	0.136	0.134	0.136
55	0.214	0.215	0.213	0.215	0.147	0.148	0.147	0.148
60	0.236	0.237	0.236	0.237	0.161	0.162	0.161	0.162
65	0.263	0.263	0.263	0.263	0.179	0.179	0.179	0.179
70	0.295	0.295	0.295	0.295	0.199	0.199	0.198	0.199
75	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.222	0.222	0.222	0.222
80	0.379	0.379	0.378	0.378	0.249	0.249	0.248	0.248
85	0.432	0.432	0.431	0.431	0.278	0.278	0.278	0.278
90	0.493	0.493	0.493	0.493	0.310	0.310	0.310	0.310

4.1.1 A note on temporary aggregate measures

Life expectancy, life disparity, entropy and the Gini coefficient have also *temporary* equivalents (see, for example, Shkolnikov and Andreev (2010) and the references therein) that characterize the distribution of deaths in a given finite age interval $[x, X]$, $x \geq 0$, $X < \infty$. Computationally, the only difference

in comparison to [9]-[12] is the integration over $[x, X]$ instead of $[x, \infty)$. The smaller the length of the interval, the bigger changes in fitted survival curves among models can be detected. As a result, the presence of a Makeham term affects to a much greater extent temporary e^\dagger and H (containing $\ln s(x)$ in the integrand).

4.2 Mortality measures affected by misspecification

Misspecified models from the Gompertz family, i.e., models that disregard a non-zero Makeham term c or a non-zero frailty parameter γ , lead to biased parameter estimators. Even if the fit of the observed death rates by the estimated force of mortality is satisfactory, single-parameter estimates $\hat{\theta}$ that are not capturing the true θ may lead to wrong calculations of mortality measures in which parameters θ are involved. The rate of individual aging, captured by b , and the level of mortality at the starting age of analysis (a for G, Γ G and $a + c$ for GM, Γ GM) are the simplest examples. Other mortality measures that can be distorted by model misspecification include the life-table aging rate (LAR) and the modal age at death.

4.2.1 Rate of individual aging b

The rate of individual aging is defined as the relative derivative of the hazard that accounts for the aging process (Vaupel, 2010). In a Gompertz-family framework the hazard of death by senescent causes is captured by the Gompertz function ae^{bx} , and thus the rate of individual aging equals b . Figure 3 illustrates the effect of neglecting the Makeham term: without accounting for c , the individual rate of aging for Swedish females seems to be almost steadily increasing from about 0.06 to 0.115 over 160 years, while the inclusion of an age-independent hazard suggests that b has been fluctuating in narrower bounds. The Γ GM estimate for the rate of individual aging might be speaking to some extent in favor of Vaupel's hypothesis that b may be a biological constant (Vaupel, 2010, p. 539, Box 1). However, even if the b -hypothesis is true, most probably the rates of individual aging for males and females are different (see Tables 5 and 6), both for overall and cause-specific mortality (Missov and Ribeiro, 2016). The estimation of the individual rate of aging for human populations is sensitive not only to model choice, but also to the starting age of analysis (Tables 5 and 6): if the starting age is located in the front-end of the log-Gompertz line or to the interval where mortality deceleration starts, the estimates of b tends to be higher.

Figure 3 – The rate of individual aging b estimated for Swedish females (Data source: HMD, 2015), ages 30-110 (top), ages 40-110 (middle), and ages 50-110 (bottom). The red triangles denote \hat{b} from fitting a ΓG , while the blue circles correspond to \hat{b} from fitting a to single years

Table 5 – Estimated b and γ parameters for French females in 1999 for each model of the Gompertz family. All models were fitted from different starting ages x onwards (column 1) and the four mortality measures were calculated by [9]-[12] using the survival functions with the corresponding estimated parameters

x	b			γ		
	G	GM	FG	FGM	FG	FGM
25	0.109	0.123	0.109	0.125	0.000	0.020
30	0.110	0.124	0.110	0.129	0.000	0.045
35	0.111	0.126	0.111	0.134	0.000	0.076
40	0.113	0.128	0.113	0.139	0.000	0.109
45	0.115	0.129	0.115	0.144	0.000	0.138
50	0.118	0.130	0.118	0.149	0.000	0.164
55	0.121	0.130	0.122	0.153	0.016	0.187
60	0.123	0.128	0.128	0.156	0.052	0.205
65	0.125	0.125	0.134	0.158	0.094	0.213
70	0.126	0.126	0.141	0.159	0.135	0.219
75	0.125	0.125	0.147	0.156	0.168	0.208
80	0.120	0.120	0.155	0.155	0.209	0.210
85	0.112	0.112	0.150	0.150	0.187	0.187
90	0.098	0.098	0.141	0.141	0.156	0.154

Table 6 – Estimated b and γ parameters for French males in 1999 when fitting each model of the Gompertz family. All models were fitted from different starting ages x onwards (column 1) and the four mortality measures were calculated by [9]-[12] using the survival functions with the corresponding estimated parameters

x	b			γ		
	G	GM	FG	FGM	FG	FGM
25	0.089	0.096	0.089	0.096	0.000	0.000
30	0.090	0.097	0.090	0.097	0.000	0.000
35	0.090	0.099	0.090	0.099	0.000	0.000
40	0.091	0.102	0.091	0.102	0.000	0.000
45	0.092	0.104	0.092	0.104	0.000	0.000
50	0.094	0.106	0.094	0.107	0.000	0.010
55	0.096	0.107	0.096	0.111	0.000	0.031
60	0.098	0.109	0.098	0.118	0.000	0.061
65	0.100	0.110	0.100	0.132	0.000	0.120
70	0.103	0.109	0.104	0.147	0.011	0.182
75	0.106	0.106	0.116	0.146	0.073	0.177
80	0.105	0.105	0.135	0.136	0.155	0.157
85	0.098	0.098	0.131	0.131	0.134	0.134
90	0.086	0.086	0.126	0.131	0.121	0.131

Table 7 – Estimated b and γ parameters for simulated data (Γ GM with $a = 0.00002$, $b = 0.11$, $c = 0.004$, $\gamma = 0.02$) when fitting each model of the Gompertz family. All models were fitted from different starting ages x onwards (column 1) and the four mortality measures were calculated by [9]-[12] using the survival functions with the corresponding estimated parameters.

x	b			γ		
	G	GM	Γ G	Γ GM	Γ G	Γ GM
25	0.102	0.108	0.102	0.110	0.000	0.020
30	0.102	0.108	0.102	0.110	0.000	0.020
35	0.103	0.108	0.103	0.110	0.000	0.019
40	0.104	0.108	0.104	0.110	0.000	0.020
45	0.105	0.108	0.105	0.110	0.000	0.021
50	0.105	0.108	0.105	0.110	0.000	0.021
55	0.106	0.108	0.106	0.110	0.000	0.022
60	0.106	0.108	0.106	0.110	0.000	0.022
65	0.107	0.108	0.107	0.110	0.003	0.022
70	0.107	0.107	0.108	0.110	0.008	0.020
75	0.107	0.107	0.108	0.110	0.011	0.021
80	0.107	0.107	0.108	0.110	0.014	0.021
85	0.107	0.107	0.109	0.109	0.017	0.018
90	0.107	0.107	0.109	0.109	0.017	0.017

For Γ GM model estimation we use the raw death counts instead of the Kannisto-smoothed HMD counts because the latter imposes a logistic model (the Γ GM and Kannisto models are statistically indistinguishable) on the data. The instability of the Γ GM-estimates of b and γ for the 1999 French population can most probably be attributed to the fluctuation of raw death counts at the oldest ages, especially when the starting age of analysis is high. The positive correlation between the maximum-likelihood estimators of b and γ is also reflected in higher estimates of b when the model “detects” a higher γ . The latter takes place when the models are fitted from a later age when the likelihood accounts better for mortality deceleration. For simulated data, the Γ GM-estimates of b and γ are much more robust with respect to the starting age of analysis as death-count fluctuations at the highest ages are minimal. The instability of b -estimates for France in 1999 might be also attributed to an age-dependent individual rate of aging. The existence of the latter, though, is very hard to be verified as a model with an additional $b(x)$ vector of parameters for a single year (or cohort) will be overparameterized and, therefore, not statistically feasible.

4.2.2 Degree of heterogeneity

The degree of heterogeneity in the study population is captured by γ ,

the squared coefficient of variation (variance over squared expectation) of the single-parameter gamma distribution used to model frailty in ΓG and ΓGM . While the average frailty and frailty's variance vary with age x , the coefficient of variation stays the same - this is an exclusive property of the gamma distribution. Tables 5-6 contain γ -estimates for French females and males, respectively, in 1999 while Table 7 presents the γ -estimates in the simulation study introduced in section 4.1. For simulated data (Table 7), the ΓG model does not "detect" the actual degree of heterogeneity, especially at starting ages below 85, while the ΓGM model seems to capture the true γ for all starting ages up to 80 (inclusive). Fitting a frailty model after age 85 seems to lead to slightly underestimated values of b , perhaps due to substantial data fluctuation. For the 1999 French data (Tables 5 and 6), γ -estimates are extremely sensitive to the starting age of analysis - for lower starting ages the ΓG and, to a lesser extent, the ΓGM model detect little or no heterogeneity at all. As already discussed in 4.2.1, most probably this is due to data fluctuation at the oldest ages.

4.2.3 Rate of Population Aging (LAR)

The life-table aging rate (LAR) measures the age-specific pace of mortality change. It is the rate of population aging as opposed to b , the rate of individual aging in a Gompertz-family framework. LAR is defined as the relative derivative of the marginal hazard (Horiuchi and Coale, 1990)

$$LAR(x) = \frac{\frac{d}{dx}\mu(x)}{\mu(x)} = \frac{d}{dx} \ln \mu(x),$$

where $\mu(x)$ denotes [1], [2], [5], or [6]. For contemporary populations $LAR(x)$ has a bell-shaped pattern for ages 50+ (Horiuchi and Wilmoth, 1997), and the peak of the curve corresponds to the age of mortality deceleration. Note that $LAR(x) \equiv b$ for $\mu(x) = ae^{bx}$ and, as a result, G can be eliminated as a good approximation to the bell-shaped empirical LAR that is calculated from life tables by

$$LAR_{emp}(x) = \ln M(x) - \ln M(x-1),$$

where $M(x)$ is the central death rate at age x . The GM model does not provide an adequate fit either, as $LAR(x)$ in this case has a logistic S-shape. As a result, when it comes to reconstructing human LAR patterns, it is uncommon to leave γ out of the model (Ribeiro and Missov, 2016), even though some studies find no compelling evidence for the existence of mortality deceleration (Gavrilov and Gavrilova, 2011; Gavrilova and Gavrilov, 2015).

Neglecting the Makeham term, though, is not uncommon as the presence of c makes the estimation procedure more complicated: researchers prefer fitting a ΓG (to a ΓGM) from a later starting age at which c is supposedly zero to avoid fitting a non-linear model. Fitting a ΓG results in a concave LAR curve that decreases monotonically, i.e., it does not capture the age of mortality deceleration at all. As a result, the only model of the *Gompertz family* that captures the bell shape of the empirical LAR for humans after age 50 (Horiuchi and Wilmoth, 1997) is the ΓGM . The latter speaks in favor of non-negligible background mortality at age 50 and subsequent mortality deceleration at older ages.

4.2.4 Modal age at death

The old-age mortality mode M is the age at which the largest proportion of senescent deaths occur. Unlike life expectancy at birth $e(0)$, i.e., the average lifespan, the modal age at death M is not influenced by infant and young-adult (excessive) mortality. As a result, usually $M > e(0)$. Knowing M is important because this is the age around which hospitals, nursing homes, and public health in general spend most of their resources.

The modal age at death can be distorted if we fit a G model instead of a ΓG (Figure 4). The G model overestimates M , and the degree of overestimation depends on the magnitude of the neglected frailty term: if $\gamma = 0.2$, a common value for HMD populations, M gets overestimated by almost 2 years. The effect is similar if we fit a GM model instead of a ΓGM (Figure 5).

Neglecting the Makeham term also results in biased estimates for the modal age at death. As a consequence of fitting a G model instead of a GM (Figure 6), M is underestimated. The degree of underestimation depends on the magnitude of the neglected Makeham term: for $c = 0.001$ the difference is almost 2 years, while for a much smaller Makeham term $c = 0.00002$ (a less realistic value for human populations) the underestimation is less than two weeks.

Fitting a ΓG model instead of a ΓGM results in correct estimation of M when γ is high in comparison to c (Figure 7, top right panel). Note that the larger the Makeham term, the more deaths are predicted to take place at ages lower than M (Figure 7, top left and bottom panels).

Figure 4 – Distribution of deaths of estimated G (green curve) and ΓG (blue curve) models. The data are simulated from ΓG models with parameters $a = 0.00002$, $b = 0.09$, $\gamma = 0$ (right). The red triangles correspond to the true density, and the dashed lines show the estimated modes (exact values presented in the top left corner of each plot)

Figure 5 – Distribution of deaths of estimated GM (green curve) and Γ GM (blue curve) models. The data are simulated from Γ GM models with parameters $a = 0.00002$, $b = 0.09$, $c = 0.001$, $\gamma = 0.2$ (left) and $\gamma = 0.1$ (right). The red triangles correspond to the true density, and the dashed lines show the estimated modes (exact values presented in the top left corner of each plot)

Figure 6 – Distribution of deaths of estimated G (green curve) and GM (blue curve) models. The data are simulated from GM models with parameters $a = 0.00002$, $b = 0.09$, $c = 0.001$ (left) and $c = 0.00002$ (right). The red triangles correspond to the true density, and the dashed lines show the estimated modes (values given in the top left corner of each plot)

Figure 7 – Distribution of deaths of estimated ΓG (green curve) and ΓGM (blue curve) models. The data are simulated from ΓGM models with parameters $a = 0.0002$, $b = 0.09$, $\gamma = 0.02$, $c = 0.001$ (top left) and $c = 0.00002$ (top right) as well as $a = 0.0002$, $b = 0.09$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $c = 0.001$ (bottom). The red triangles correspond to the true density, and the dashed lines show the estimated modes (values given in the top left corner of each plot)

5. CONCLUSION

Neglecting non-zero extrinsic mortality or unobserved heterogeneity distorts parameter estimates in the models from the *Gompertz family*: a is overestimated, while b is underestimated. When c is neglected, γ tends to zero as c grows. When γ is left out of the model, c is underestimated. Aggregate mortality measures like life expectancy, life disparity, entropy, and the Gini coefficient are only slightly sensitive to model misspecification and, therefore, fitting any model of the *Gompertz family* is sufficient to calculate these measures. However, the rates of individual and population aging, as well as the modal age at death can well be distorted when c or γ is neglected. In a ΓG setting, the rate of individual aging for contemporary populations is often estimated in the range of 0.10 - 0.12, but the actual b must be a little higher if c is added to the model. Moreover, to assess the true degree of heterogeneity in the study population, it is essential to include the Makeham term.

The observed mortality pattern in a given year or for a given cohort can result from 1) a heterogeneous population with a constant individual rate of aging b , 2) a homogeneous population with a varying b , i.e. $b = b(x)$, or 3) erroneous data. Estimating an age-varying b , though, is not statistically feasible as the model gets overparameterized, and, as a result, researchers studying human mortality in single years or cohorts are usually restricted to fitting models with a constant b . This article shows that among these models, it is perhaps most beneficial to choose the gamma-Gompertz-Makeham model for studying adult human mortality. If c is estimated to be zero, then background mortality is negligible, whereas a zero-estimated γ will imply that the data do not speak in favor of mortality deceleration. Fitting a ΓGM will also eliminate all problems associated with wrong calculation of all characteristics of the mortality distribution.

Acknowledgements

We thank James W. Vaupel, Hal Caswell, Maciej J. Danko, and Oskar Burger for their comments on different versions of the manuscript

References

- BEARD R.E. (1959), "Note on Some Mathematical Mortality Models", in WOOLSTENHOLME G.E.W., O'CONNOR M. (eds.), *The Lifespan of Animals*, Little, Brown and Company, Boston, 302-311.

- BRILLINGER D.R. (1986), “The Natural Variability of Vital Rates and Associated Statistics”, *Biometrics*, 42(4): 693-734.
- DUCHATEAU L., JANSSEN P. (2008), *The Frailty Model*, Springer, New York.
- FINKELSTEIN M.S., ESAULOVA V. (2006), “Asymptotic Behavior of a General Class of Mixture Failure Rates”, *Advances in Applied Probability*, 38, 242-262.
- GAVRILOV L.A., GAVRILOVA N.S. (2011), “Mortality Measurement at Advanced Ages: A Study of the Social Security Administration Death Master File”, *North American Actuarial Journal*, 15(3): 442-447.
- GAVRILOVA N.S., GAVRILOV L.A. (2015), “Biodemography of Old-Age Mortality in Humans and Rodents”, *J Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci*, 70(1): 1-9.
- GINI C. (1912), “Variabilità e mutabilità”, *Studi Economico-Giuridici dell’Università di Cagliari*, 3, 1-158.
- GOMPERTZ B. (1825), “On the Nature of the Function Expressive of the Law of Human Mortality, and on a New Mode of Determining the Value of Life Contingencies”, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*, 115, 513-583.
- HMD (2015), *The Human Mortality Database*, <http://www.mortality.org/>, 2015.
- HORIUCHI S., COALE A.J. (1990), “Age Patterns of Mortality for Older Women: An Analysis Using the Age-Specific Rate of Mortality Change with Age”, *Mathematical Population Studies*, 2(4): 245-267.
- HORIUCHI S., WILMOTH J.R. (1997), “Age Patterns of the Life Table Aging Rate for Major Causes of Death in Japan, 1951-1990”, *Journal of Gerontology, Biological Sciences*, 52A(1), B67-B77.
- KEYFITZ N. (1977), *Applied Mathematical Demography*, Willey-Blackwell, New York.
- LENART A., MISSOV T.I. (2014), “Goodness-of-Fit Tests for the Gompertz Distribution”, *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, advance online publication March 3, 2014, doi: 10.1080/03610926.2014.892323.
- MAKEHAM W.M. (1860), “On the law of mortality and the construction of annuity tables”, *Journal of the Institute of Actuaries*, 8, 301-310.
- McCULLAGH P., NELDER J.A. (1989), *Generalized Linear Model*, Chapman & Hall, London, 2nd edition.
- MISSOV T.I. (2013), “Gamma-Gompertz Life Expectancy at Birth”, *Demographic Research*, 28(9): 259-270.
- MISSOV T.I., FINKELSTEIN M. (2011), “Admissible Mixing Distributions for a General Class of Mixture Survival Models with Known Asymptotics”, *Theoretical Population Biology*, 80(1): 64-70.
- MISSOV T.I., LENART A. (2013), “Gompertz-Makeham Life Expectancies: Expressions and Applications”, *Theoretical Population Biology*, 90, 29-35.

- MISSOV T.I., LENART A., NÉMETH L., CANUDAS-ROMO V., VAUPEL J.W. (2015), "The Gompertz Force of Mortality in Terms of the Modal Age at Death", *Demographic Research*, 32(36): 1031-1048.
- MISSOV T.I., NÉMETH L., DAŃKO M.J. (2016), "How Much Can We Trust Life Tables? Sensitivity of Mortality Measures to Right-Censoring Treatment", *Palgrave Communications*, 2:15049.
- MISSOV T.I., RIBEIRO F. (2016), "Do We Age at the Same Rate? Findings from Cause-of-Death Data", *Demography* (forthcoming).
- MULLEN K.M., ARDIA D., GIL D.L., WINDOVER D., CLINE J. (2011), "DEoptim: An R Package for Global Optimization by Differential Evolution", *Journal of Statistical Software*, 40(6): 1-26.
- RIBEIRO F., MISSOV T.I. (2016), "Revisiting Mortality Deceleration Patterns in a Gamma-Gompertz-Makeham Framework", in SCHOEN, R. (ed.), *Dynamic Demographic Analysis*, Springer Series on Demographic Methods and Population Analysis, Springer, New York.
- SHKOLNIKOV V., ANDREEV E. (2010), "Spreadsheet for calculation of life-table dispersion measures", *MPIDR Technical Report*, <http://www.demogr.mpg.de/papers/technicalreports/tr-2010-001.pdf>.
- STEINSALTZ D.R., WACHTER K.W. (2006), "Understanding Mortality Rate Deceleration and Heterogeneity", *Mathematical Population Studies*, 13, 19-37.
- STORN R., PRICE K. (1997), "Differential evolution - a simple and efficient heuristic for global optimization over continuous spaces", *Journal of Global Optimization*, 11, 341-359.
- VAUPEL J.W. (2002), "Life Expectancy at Current Rates vs Current Conditions: A Reflexion Stimulated by Bongaarts and Feeney's 'How Long Do We Live?'"', *Demographic Research*, 7, 365-378.
- VAUPEL J.W., MANTON K.G., STALLARDE. (1979), "The Impact of Heterogeneity in Individual Frailty on the Dynamics of Mortality", *Demography*, 16, 439-454.
- VAUPEL J.W. (2010), "Biodemography of Human Ageing", *Nature*, 464, 536-542.
- VAUPEL J.W., MISSOV T.I. (2014), "Unobserved Population Heterogeneity: A Review of Formal Relationships", *Demographic Research*, 31(22): 659-686.
- WIENKE A. (2010), *Frailty Models in Survival Analysis*, Chapman & Hall/ CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL.
- WILMOTH J.R., ANDREEV K., JDANOV D., GLEI D.A., BOE C., BUBENHEIM M., PHILIPOV D., SHKOLNIKOV V., VACHON P. (2007), "Methods Protocol for the Human Mortality Database", <http://www.mortality.org/Public/Docs/MethodsProtocol.pdf>